

PEMERIKSAAN GRAMMAR, CITATION CHECK, DAN ORIGINALITAS NASKAH DENGAN AI

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UIN Salatiga

TUJUAN PRESENTASI INI

- Memahami pentingnya pemeriksaan grammar
- Mengetahui cara citation check
- Mempelajari pemeriksaan originalitas
- Mengenal tools AI

MENGAPA GRAMMAR, CITATION, DAN ORIGINALITAS PENTING?

- **Grammar:** meningkatkan kejelasan dan kredibilitas (special for **non-native of English**)
- **Citation Check:** memastikan keakuratan sumber
- **Originality Check:** menjaga integritas akademik
- Standar publikasi menuntut ketiga aspek ini

PEMERIKSAAN GRAMMAR BAHASA INGGRIS

- Memastikan struktur kalimat sesuai kaidah
- Memperbaiki kejelasan (**clarity aspect**)
- Menghindari kesalahan sintaksis
- Menyesuaikan gaya bahasa akademik

THE STORY OF MPU SPOON

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Cunggurang Inscription Site **which one is correct: Mpu Spoon or Mpu Sendok?**

The Cunggurang inscription is an inscription issued by Sri Maharaja Rakai Hino Sri Isana Wikramadharmottungga or commonly called **Mpu spoon** in 851 saka or 929 AD in Old Javanese. This inscription was found on the eastern slope of Mount Penanggungan or to be precise in the hamlet of Sukci, Bukusari village, Gempol district, Pasuruan district.

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TIMUN MAS OR GOLDEN CUCUMBER?

PHILOLOGY

Journal of English Language and Literature

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THE MAIN IDEAS OF INDONESIAN FOLKLORES: *THE ONION AND THE GARLIC, THE MALIN KUNDANG AND THE GOLDEN CUCUMBER*

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Abstract

The research studies the main ideas by using qualitative descriptive method in Indonesian Folklore: The Onion And The Garlic, The Malin Kundang, And The Golden Cucumber. Indonesian Folklore is just the same as other stories, starting with an introduction, accompanied by a body of essay and ended by conclusion. The sequence

NORMS

The development of technology has brought human beings to live in two social realities: traditional and virtual society. The ~~second society~~ virtual emerges as a result of the intersection between the efforts of conventional (non-virtual) ~~society to meet their society, in meeting~~ needs and ~~technology, especially information technology developing technologies~~ (Shayo, Olfman, Iriberry, & Igbaria, 2007, p. 206). WAGs ~~can be is~~ categorized into cybernetic organizations of virtual societies. Virtual has become a term ~~to define for defining~~ social ~~forms-norms~~, in which members do not have to live, meet, or work together directly ("face to face"), ~~in order~~ to produce goods, services, or maintain social relationships (Shayo et al., 2007, p. 187). As an organization, WAGs have common goals that are communicated virtually. ~~Organization-Also, organization~~ aims ~~enable a group of people to coordinate efficiently and effectively to achieve their goals-common purpose~~ (Shayo et al., 2007, p. 204).

WAGs, like other community groups, commonly have moral orders to maintain proper social ~~behaviors~~ behaviours. Garfinkel (1964, p. 225) ~~argues-stated~~ that social and moral orders are "natural facts of life" ~~to determine for determining~~ what is right and wrong. Moral orders are rules that regulate the daily activities of certain members of ~~the society; the~~ The members are sometimes not aware of their presence, "perceivably natural normal courses of action" which are accepted together as they are ("take it for granted") (Garfinkel, 1984, p. 225). Social actions and meanings that members of ~~the society~~ recognize-recognized form the moral orders of a ~~group or society; group, which enables~~ the ~~moral orders-enable group members to evaluate social practices good/bad, appropriate/inappropriate, polite, less polite, over-polite, impolite, etc.~~ (Kádár & Haugh, 2013, p.94).

Moral ~~order-consists-orders consist~~ of three layers of norms, namely ~~norms-of~~ individuals, ~~norms-of~~ groups/organizations/communities, and ~~norms-of~~ society/culture (Kádár & Haugh, 2013, p. 95). Furthermore, Kadar and Haugh ~~argue-stated~~ that the first norm is formed from the history of interactions between individuals ~~who may that~~ have similarities with or differences from one another. ~~On the second level this norm is a set of expectations~~

(MANA SUBYEKNYA?) IN THE PAST CENTURY **SAW** THAT EUROPE ASSOCIATES THEMSELVES AS...

Article

PDF Available

A suggestion that Europe also a Muslim: a study from historical and contemporary perspectives

May 2019 · Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies 9(1):83

DOI:10.18326/ijjims.v9i1.83-110

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Authors:

Muhammad Awalluddin
MARA University of Technology

Anisa Safiah Maznorbalia

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TOOLS AI UNTUK GRAMMAR CHECK

- **Grammarly**: grammar, spelling, tone suggestion
- **QuillBot Grammar Checker**: grammar + paraphrasing

GRAMMARLY CHECK

◀ A suggestion that Europe also a Muslim: a study from historical and contemporary perspectives

Abstract and Figures

In the past century saw that Europe associates themselves as a Christian domain until now. The proclamation of Edict of Thessalonica in 380 AD made the Nicene Christianity as the state in Roman Empire and saw a transition from paganism to a Christian domain or Christendom. Since its inception, several edict has been enacted and several peace treaties have been broken to diminish an idea of multiculturalism within theirs faith land. The establishment of Muslim rules in Iberian Peninsula has changed the dominion of Christian. Muslims in Spain introduced convivencia, which saw that Abrahamic religions, Islam, Judaism and Christianity co-exist together, removing racial, cultural and religious barriers to embrace each other that nurture spirit of inclusion. The Golden Age of Muslim Civilization evidence that Cordova has become a center of Europe, perhaps the world for scientific knowledge advancement. Subsequently, contribute for Renaissance Age in Europe. Additionally, fall of Constantinople in 1453 under Ottomans reshaping the geographcial of Europe and permanently marked the term of European Islam. Through tedious analysis on

Grammarly

• CORRECTNESS: GRAMMAR

is also

There may be a verb use issue here.

• saw that · Correct the verb

• associates · Change the form of the verb

• themselves · Correct pronoun usage

• proclamation · Correct your spelling

• Edict · Correct article usage

62 All basic issues 19 Premium issues

PARAPHRASING TOOLS

AI Paraphrasing & Rewording Tool⁺

Effortlessly reword, rephrase, and improve your writing with AI-powered accuracy.

Modes: **Standard** Fluency English (US) ^

Synonyms:

In the past century saw that Europe associates themselves as a Christian domain until now. The proclamation of Edict of Thessalonica in 380 AD made the Nicene Christianity as the state in Roman Empire and saw a transition from paganism to a Christian domain or Christendom. Since its inception, several edict has been enacted and several peace treaties have been broken to diminish an idea of multiculturalism within their faith land. The establishment of Muslim rules in Iberian Peninsula has changed the dominion of Christian. Muslims in

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For unlimited words, Use [QuillBot](#)

Paraphrase

Advanced Paraphrase

- 1. <https://quillbot.com/>
- 2. <https://plagiarismdetector.net/paraphrasing-tool>
- 3. <https://paraphrasing-tool.com/>
- 4. <https://www.duplichecker.com/article-rewriter.php>
- 5. <https://www.rewritertools.com/paraphrasing-tool>

CITATION CHECK

- Memverifikasi format sitasi sesuai gaya
- Menghindari mismatched citations
- Memastikan akurasi nama penulis, tahun, sumber
- Bagi pengelola jurnal, Pastikan author Mematuhi standar publikasi dan article template

CITESURE - CITATION VERIFICATION

Check your citations in seconds

Don't get caught out by **fake citations**

 Verify

 Search (Beta)

 Humanise

Syahriyani, A., Fahri, A., Putratama, M. R., & Amaliyah, M. (2022). Squid game series as social phenomenon on Twitter: A study of participatory culture. *International journal of media and information literacy*, 7(2), 578-588.

1/3 citations per batch

[Verify Citations →](#)

Verification Results

Syahriyani, A., Fahri, A., Putratama, M. R., & Amaliyah, M. (2022). Squid game series as social phenomenon on Twitter: A study of participatory culture. *International journal of media and information literacy*, 7(2), 578-588.

Valid

83% High Validity ⓘ

No Replacements Needed

ALTERNATIVE REFERENCE CHECKER

• <https://nurscienceinstitute.id/reference-checker/>

Reference Checker Nur Science Institute

Biden's Speech: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *ELTALL: English Language Teaching, Applied Linguistic and Literature*, 5(2), 192-211.

Barus, J. (2022). Types of Euphemism in Anies Baswedan's Speech. *ITQAN: Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Kependidikan*, 13(2), 277-288. <https://doi.org/10.47766/itqan.v14i1.421>.

Becker, A., & Bieswanger, M. (2006). *Introduction to English Linguistics*. Francke.

Burridge, K. (2012). Euphemism and language change: The sixth and seventh ages. *Lexis: Journal in English Lexicology*, 7, 65 - 92.

Cambridge Dictionary Online. (2025). *Cambridge Dictionary | English Dictionary, Translations & Thesaurus*. (Accessed: April 22 - May 31, 2025).

Candra, S. I., Arifin, M. B., & Asanti, C. (2022). Euphemism Expressed by the Characters of Shakespeare in Love Movie Script. *Ilmu Budaya: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra, Seni, dan Budaya*, 6(1), 57-71.

Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*. SAGE Publications.

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Galvin, K. (2024, November 4). Vice President Kamala Harris asks voters to 'turn the page' on Donald Trump. *The Eagle Online Article*. <https://www.theeagleonline.com/article/2024/11/vice-president-kamala-harris-asks-voters-to-turn-the-page-on-donald-trump>. (Accessed on: May 1, 2025).

Generate Reference List

Check All References

Export as PDF

Allan, K., & Burridge, K. (1991). *Euphemism & Dysphemism: Language Used as Shield and Weapon*. Oxford University Press.

Found in Google Scholar

Check

Amanda, R. A., & Handayani, T. (2024). *Language, Power, and Ideology on Joe*

Found in Google Scholar

Check

Biden's Speech: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *ELTALL: English Language Teaching, Applied Linguistic and Literature*, 5(2), 192-211.

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Found in Google Scholar

Check

PEMERIKSAAN ORIGINALITAS NASKAH

- **Mencegah plagiarisme & Menjamin integritas akademik** : Memastikan karya yang diajukan tidak menyalin atau menjiplak karya orang lain
- **Memastikan orisinalitas dan kualitas ide**: Memverifikasi bahwa gagasan, temuan dan argumen yang disampaikan benar-benar hasil pemikiran sendiri dan berkualitas bukan plagiasi ide ide yang sudah ada.
- **Menghormati hak cipta**: Menghindari pelanggaran hak cipta dan masalah hukum yang mungkin timbul karena right violance.
- **Memperbaiki kesalahan kutipan**: Mengidentifikasi bagian yang kurang tepat dalam penulisan sumber atau sitasi sehingga bisa diperbaiki sebelum diterbitkan.

TOOLS AI UNTUK ORIGINALITY CHECK

- Turnitin: standar internasional
- iThenticate: untuk publikasi ilmiah jurnal
- - Grammarly Premium: originality + grammar
- - PlagScan / Copyleaks: mendukung banyak bahasa

CONTOH SIMILARITY SCORE 18% TAPI AI CHECK 78%?

The screenshot displays the Turnitin Feedback Studio interface. The main document area shows the title "JOURNAL OF LINGUISTICS, CULTURE AND COMMUNICATION" with a red box around the word "CULTURE" and a red "2" above it. Below the title, the volume and ISSN information are visible: "Vol.xx, No.xx, Year: Month: pages, E-ISSN: 2988-1641" and the URL "https://jolcc.org/index.php/jolcc/index".

The document content includes:

2. No – if the article does not meet the quality criteria.

This assessment helped ensure that only high-quality, recent, and thematically relevant studies were included in the literature review, supporting a focused and comprehensive analysis.

DISCUSSION

To explore the role of Wordwall in enhancing student engagement in English language learning, eight relevant journal articles were reviewed. These studies, published between 2023 and 2025, were selected based on their focus on the implementation of Wordwall. Table 1 presents a summary of the reviewed articles, including their titles, years of publication, publishers, and authors.

The right sidebar shows the "Match Overview" panel with a total similarity score of 18%. Below this, a list of sources is shown with their respective similarity percentages:

Rank	Source	Similarity Score
1	jolcc.org (Internet Source)	4%
2	Submitted to UIN Rade... (Student Paper)	3%
3	repository.pip-semaran... (Internet Source)	1%
4	educare.unidhas.ac.id (Internet Source)	1%
5	Submitted to Queen Ma... (Student Paper)	1%
6	ojs.fkipummy.ac.id (Internet Source)	1%
7	ijere.iaescore.com (Internet Source)	1%
8	ejournal.undikma.ac.id (Internet Source)	1%
9	doaj.org (Internet Source)	1%
10	Mails D.H. Rahiem. "To... (Publication)	<1%
11	Pak, Aloe. "Revitalizing ... (Publication)	<1%
12	Submitted to Keen Univ... (Student Paper)	<1%

The bottom of the screen shows the Turnitin AI check results: "AI 78%". The page footer indicates "Page: 6 of 14" and "Word Count: 3778". The system tray shows the date and time as "5:25 PM 8/6/2025".

INTEGRASI AI DALAM TIGA PEMERIKSAAN

- Gunakan Grammarly/LanguageTool untuk grammar
- Gunakan Mendeley/Zotero untuk citation reference manager
- Gunakan Turnitin/iThenticate untuk originalitas
- - Workflow: Tulis → Cek Grammar → masukkan sitasi dan tata Citation → cek Originality → Revisi lagi

TIPS EFEKTIF MENGGUNAKAN AI

- Jangan bergantung 100% pada AI
- Setting bahasa dan dialek sesuai misal English (US) atau English (UK). misal Tandfonline.com mintanya dialek Eng-UK.
- - Perbarui database referensi
- - AI sebagai assistant, bukan replacement

PENUTUP

- Grammar, citation, dan originalitas penting untuk kualitas karya
- - AI mempermudah proses, tapi tetap butuh evaluasi manusia (Human Editor is irreplaceable)
- - Kombinasi skill manusia + AI = hasil optimal